

CONCEPTUAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR COMPREHENSIVE AND COOPERATIVE CRAWLING AND INDEXING THE WEB

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Abstract

The web is a very large and dynamic digital database. Currently there are about 341 million domains registered in a bit more than 1500 top level domains (TLDs)². The .com TLD alone accounts for 155 million registered domains (46%). As few as 65 TLDs together account for 95% of all registered domains. Assuming an average of 250 documents/pages per domain, the current Web consists of an estimated 85 billion documents or pages. Beyond this, the Web of course stores petabytes of media data with images, films, voice/music recordings, social media data as well as petabytes of public data bases with scientific data, satellite imagery and administrative data in the ‘deeper’ part of the web.

As of today, the Web is a very dynamic digital ecosystem, which is influenced by different organisations, governments, individuals and a few monopolistic commercial entities, with different, often contradicting interests. This makes the Web a very innovative, however, partially even toxic environment. Particularly, since a few monopolistic gatekeepers control access to information on the web and shape corresponding access patterns, while the innovation potential and core value is generated by the enormous number of individual or organisational contributors. This structure puts pressure on those small contributors in science, economy, art, culture, media and society, to follow either the rules of the gatekeepers, or get lost in the vastness of the digital space. Consequently, information as public good, with free, open and unbiased access – one of the core principles that the Web was built on – currently is in the hand of a few corporate entities along with the (commercial) interest of their shareholders.

Based on this analysis we argue, that unbiased access to digital data and information requires a collaborative effort of a variety of different organisations to build an open index and metadata pool of the Web. Such an open web index will be the basis for open search engines, a diversity of public and commercial web services, science, training of AI and many future applications we can’t even think of today – while at the same time decreasing the dependency on the current monopolistic gatekeepers.

In this talk we discuss concepts and approaches for aligning efforts, currently ongoing in parallel, in an open and democratic manner, to jointly build and maintain a comprehensive and open index for the web. Such an activity will involve a large number of public, scientific

and commercial organisations in a large-scale cooperative effort.

Generating a complete index of the Web is typically beyond the capacity of single organisation, not only because of the high technical complexity, but more so, due to the high associated costs. However, we argue that one can generate a comprehensive web index and web data pool by combining ongoing and dedicated efforts of individual organisations and by integrating public computing facilities into the task. To achieve this, we suggest concentrating first on the surface web and aiming at 80% of completeness for a large-scale cooperative web-crawling and indexing campaign. To set this up, two key questions need to be answered: (i) What is the most efficient way to share and distribute such a comprehensive web crawling and indexing effort, while minimizing network load and ensuring energy-efficient hosting, sharing and updating of the distributed web index? (ii) How to develop a value-oriented service-based ecosystem - beyond monopolistic actors - around such an open web index and how to recover the costs for generating and maintaining such a web index?

There are different strategic options for distributing the tasks in a scalable peer to peer framework, allowing for an overall trade-off between individual/voluntary support and achieving the common greater goal. Crawling and indexing goals of contributing computing and science centres may be different, however, as long as the synergy with the larger group is beneficial, there is a win-win situation in contributing to the larger group effort and its goals. It will be important to find a good match between such voluntary participation and financial remuneration to sustain the needed computational capacities.

Technically we suggest a decentralised approach, splitting the overall task vertically, i.e. along the necessary computing tasks, and horizontally, i.e. focusing on different sub-parts of the Web. Vertical splits involve coordinated crawling of sub-parts of the Web, storage (and access) to crawls (i.e. via WARC files), processing and enriching crawls as well as the coordinated generation of indices and sub-indices. In order to generate meaningful, manageable and shareable web crawls, web repositories, web indices and web graphs, the task has to be shared among dozens of computing facilities. It will be important to consistently enrich the web indices with a substantial and extensible number of pre-processed signals and attributes, such as nominal age group, ethical annotations,

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² <https://research.domaintools.com/statistics/tld-counts/> (access on 18.6.2021)

comprehensive geo-tagging and many more. An open web index will fuel not only the creation of specific search engines, but also will also reduce efforts in creating AI products, like for example knowledge graphs or neuronal language models. In return, those efforts can contribute to improving the index of the web.

In the talk we discuss different strategies for dividing the generation and maintenance of a global, still distributed, open web index. Candidate factors are: division by language, TLD, geographic region, topic/application field, network topology/latency, hosting facilities etc. Of course, also the type of contributing computing centres and overall funding and governance scheme of the cooperative effort will be of relevance for sharing of tasks: Public science and computing centres may have a different mandate and motivation to contribute to the joint undertaking than e.g. private Internet service providers, industry or fully commercial computing facilities.

Finally, we discuss, how the division of tasks needs to ensure that different individual web repositories and indices have relevance in itself and can be searched, queried and accessed by the cooperating entities in an energy efficient and sustainable way.